

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE FORMATION OF CONFLICT COMPETENCE IN THE TEAM OF TEACHERS OF THE INSTITUTION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article is written about to study the psychological problems of the environment of a higher education institution and to develop the components of competence related to conflicts as a condition for preventing conflicts among professors and teachers of a higher education institution. The educational program and scientific-methodological recommendations for the prevention of conflicts for professors and managers of higher education institutions were developed and covered.*

Keywords: *conflict, dispute, conflict situation, conflict competence, factors of conflict competence, ways of elimination.*

Introduction.

During the period of economic instability, political disagreements, social inequality, reform and modernization of the domestic education system, the problem of conflicts in the structure of teaching staff is of particular importance. It is characterized by a high level of conflict in the process of education and upbringing in higher educational institutions. Most educators lack the knowledge, skills, qualifications and personal qualities to help prevent and constructively resolve conflicts. This creates a risk of reducing the efficiency of the entire educational process and the quality of educational services of the university. The study of conflicts in educational institutions is very relevant, because they are an example of the whole society. The scientific solution to the problem of conflict prevention among the teaching staff of higher educational institutions is of great theoretical and practical importance for the early prediction of possible conflict situations and their professional management in educational institutions. The relevance of the formation of conflict competence as a component of the professional skills of teachers is determined by the high level of positivity of the pedagogical environment in higher educational institutions.

Literatures analysis.

From the theoretical analysis of scientific literature, it can be seen that most researchers believe that society does not exist without conflicts, because conflicts are an integral part of human existence and a source of change in society. There are different definitions of conflict. The term "conflict" comes from the Latin word "conflictus", which means "to collide". In the psychological dictionary, this concept is presented as "an updated opposition, a clash of opposing interests, goals, positions, opinions, subjects of interaction or views of opponents."

A.Ya.Antsupov and A.I.Shipilov offer the following definition: "Conflict is a negative feeling of important contradictions that arise in the process of interaction, which consists in opposing its subjects and is usually accompanied by the most decisive way to deal with them."

N. V. Grishina defines conflict as "a bipolar phenomenon (confrontation of two principles), manifested in the activities of the parties aimed at eliminating contradictions, and the parties are represented by an active subject." According to K. Boulding (an American economist and

sociologist), a conflict is understood as a situation that reports an alleged confrontation and conflict of interest, inconsistency in the positions of the parties.

According to the German scientist M. Weber, society is a set of groups that differ from each other according to their status. This creates a conflict of interests and is the cause of many social conflicts. According to M. Weber, all hopes about the possibility of eliminating them from society are illusions. Charles Darwin said that the main reason for this phenomenon in society is the natural desire of people to fight for survival.

In the middle of the 20th century, the American sociologist L. Koser explored its usefulness in his work "The Functions of Social Conflict". In his opinion, conflict is a means of defusing tension. Its result is a more accurate study of group interests. A constant source of social conflict is the lack of resources, values and prestige in any society. So as long as there are people looking for these scarce resources, there will be tension that can escalate into conflict.

E. Mayo, the founder of the theory of "human relations", emphasized that social health is a "social balance", "a state of cooperation". Such a position in society can be achieved with the help of psychological methods of creating a comfortable psychological environment in the team, a sense of satisfaction with one's work, etc.

K. Boulding identified a single universal source of conflict - the incompatibility of the needs of the parties with limited opportunities to meet them. To harmonize the situation, it is proposed to use game theory, modeling of conflict situations, etc.

A. Ya. Antsupov and A. I. Shipilov among the directions of foreign psychological studies of the conflict in the first half of the 20th century distinguish the following:

psychoanalyst (Z. Freud, A. Adler, K. Horney, E. Fromm, K. G. Jung); sociotropic (W. McDougal, S. Siegele, etc.); ethological (K. Lorenz, N. Tinbergen); the theory of group dynamics (K. Levin, D. Krech); frustration-aggressive (J. Dollard, L. Berkowitz); behavioral (A. Bandura, R. Sears), sociometric (Y. Moreno, H. Gurvich).

The psychoanalytic approach is associated with the name of the Austrian psychologist Z. Freud. He saw the main source of all social contradictions in the harmony of the human soul, the harmony between conscious and unconscious, instinctive action, moral and legal norms. In addition, Sigmund Freud says that the concept of defense mechanisms "usually refers to the methods that the ego uses in conflicts that can lead to neuroses." We all use defense mechanisms (depression suppression, regression, isolation, projection, sublimation, etc.) to help us manage stress and conflict.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the psychological and pedagogical literature, 4 stages of conflict management in educational organizations can be distinguished: 1 - forecasting, 2 - prevention, 3 - regulation, 4 - conflict resolution.

Forecasting is aimed at determining the causes of the conflict. It includes the study of objective and subjective conditions and factors of interaction between opponents, analysis of common and specific causes of conflicts between different actors. At the first stage, the following actions are effective for conflict management:

- study of individual psychological characteristics of teachers (their needs, interests, abilities, character traits, temperament, pedagogical experience, etc.);
- analysis of relationships in the team (small groups, leadership, sociometric assessment, etc.);

- study and analysis of public opinion, motives and values; know and analyze the first signs of a hidden conflict (critical statements about a conflicting person by members of the group, restrictions in communicating with him).

Conflict prevention is a type of activity aimed at preventing conflicts. It is based on predicting conflicts. If the teacher does not understand this and does not correct the situation in time, it can be fatal. Based on the information received about the causes of the conflict, active efforts are being made to neutralize the action of the entire set of determining factors.

At the stage of conflict prevention, the following actions are effective:

- neutralization measures based on a deep analysis of the causes and factors of the conflict;
- pedagogical activity - discussion, explanation, etc.;
- formation of a culture of interpersonal relations;
- administrative measures - changing working conditions, compliance of specific tasks and wages with the professional training of the conflicting party, transferring participants in the conflict to other units, etc.

At the third stage, the conflict should be regulated by the following actions:

- achieving recognition of the reality of the conflict by the conflicting person;
- remind conflicting persons to observe correct behavior in relationships;
- Negotiation;
- if necessary, involve a third party to find a solution that satisfies both parties.

There are several roles of participation of a third party in conflict resolution: arbitrator, mediator, assistant.

The arbitrator examines the nature of the problem, discusses it with the parties to the conflict, and then makes a final and binding decision.

The mediator (a mediator can be a conflict specialist or a mediator helping to resolve conflict situations by non-legal means) only organizes the negotiation process, helps to look for useful options, and the conflicting parties make the final decision.

The assistant is engaged in improving the process of discussing the problem. Does not interfere with the discussion of the content of the problem and the adoption of a final decision. So his role is not authoritarian.

ctions in the fourth stage - conflict resolution:

- *a conflict person recognizes his mistakes and shortcomings and corrects them;*
- *if it is impossible to reconcile the interests of the conflicting person with the interests of the group, he leaves the group;*
- *depending on the situation, various types of punishments, fines, etc. can be applied.*

It is known that the probability of resolution at the initial stage of the conflict (the emergence and awareness of the conflict situation) is 92%, so we emphasize once again that the conflict is easier to prevent than to resolve it. In the literature on conflict situations, a distinction is made between primary and secondary conflict prevention. Primary psychoprophylaxis consists of psychological education. Psychoprophylaxis of secondary prevention involves working in groups with a high probability of direct conflicts. In order to avoid conflicts, it is necessary to know the types of common conflict generators, for example: threats, negative assessments, teasing, rude treatment of colleagues, insults, advice, violations of ethics, etc. An important means of preventing conflicts is to characterize the behavior of conflict individuals, often suffering from

various complexes, dissatisfied with their position in society, in the family, in the organization, in need of constant satisfaction from selfishness and elimination of internal tension.

Table 1

The Structure of Conflict Competences of University Teachers

the name of the component	Cognitive	Emotional	Behavior
Development Criteria	theoretical knowledge; understanding, adequate perception of conflict, its causes and consequences in the team of teachers;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low anxiety, - friendship, - support, - believe - sympathy, - job satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - aggression, - "cooperation", - "Reconciliation" and - "avoidance" as a behavioral style, - politeness, - tolerance, - high level of conflict resistance - communication - culture

The purpose of the main part of the identification experiment is to determine the levels of development of conflict competence of teachers, the levels of development of conflict competence of teachers depending on family, demographic, national and professional factors, and the integral part is to study indicators. To solve the problems of the main part of the detecting experiment, a set of appropriate methods was used.

This method was used to assess the level of development of the cognitive component of conflict competence of teachers of higher educational institutions.

Teachers were asked to continue the sentences:

"Conflict is..." and "Conflict in the teaching staff...". A rating scale was used to process the responses. Answers are considered "correct" if they show all the important signs of conflict. If all important or unimportant characteristics are not indicated, the answer is considered "partially correct". If an important sign of conflict was not indicated or there was no answer, the answer was considered "incorrect".

The level of development of the emotional component of conflict competence was assessed by the method of assessing the psychological situation in the team, which is based on the method of semantic differential. Reactive anxiety is measured as a person's current state, while personality anxiety is measured as a stable personality trait. Personal anxiety describes the tendency to perceive a wide range of situations as threatening and to respond to such situations with a state of anxiety. Reactive anxiety is characterized by tension, nervousness. K. Horney points out that anxiety, like fear, is an emotional reaction to danger. Unlike fear, it is characterized by anxiety and uncertainty. In addition, physiological symptoms are often accompanied by a rapid heartbeat, rapid breathing, etc. This affects the nature of a person's relationship with others, increases their conflict.

The behavioral component of conflict competence was measured using express diagnostics of conflict resistance. According to a five-point rating system, the respondent shows how each characteristic manifests itself: avoidance of arguments, impartial attitude, adequate self-esteem,

correctness, etc. A high level of conflict resistance means psychological behavior in problematic and pre-conflict situations, the ability to easily communicate and support people, goodwill, cheerfulness, empathy, the ability to find a common language with different people. People with a low level of confrontation can easily get into fights over small things. Low resistance to the influence of conflict factors is a negative personality trait.

A. Assinger's test (assessment of aggressiveness in relationships) helped determine how calm or aggressive the participants in the experiment were in relationships with others. According to socio-demographic characteristics, the participants of the experiment were distributed as follows.

- by gender (men - 35.2%, women - 64.8%);
- by marital status (married - 63.4%, single - 36.6%);
- by age (20-30 years old - 16.7%, 31-40 years old - 42.6%, 41-50 years old - 28.2%, over 50 years old - 12.5%);
- 60.6% of public teachers, 39.4% of private teachers;
- teachers of humanities - 65.3%, social sciences - 34.7%.

Based on the results of the experimental part of the study, the psychological problems of the organizational environment of the university and the conditions for preventing conflicts between the teaching staff are highlighted. Surveys and interviews with teachers of higher educational institutions on various aspects of professional activity in a team of educational institutions made it possible to conduct a SWOT analysis of the organizational environment and the impact on the occurrence or prevention of conflicts, provided sufficient information to determine the factors. As shown in fig. 2.1, the idea of a SWOT analysis is to turn weaknesses into strengths and threats into opportunities.

Strengths - the strengths of the organizational environment of higher education institutions in which teachers work, as well as factors influencing the prevention of conflicts, employees emphasized the possibility of getting a good experience (45.0% of the respondents said that this is true, 31.7% answered absolutely correct). Teachers receive spiritual satisfaction from their work, regardless of the complexity of their work: 25.0% of respondents answered "no", 31.7% answered "yes", and 16.7% answered "Gri" is enough.

The work of a teacher is also good communication: this is true for 31.7%, and absolutely true for 38.3% of the respondents. 66.7% of respondents have good relations with students. Also, 40.0% of teachers liked the scoring system in their universities, 31.7% of respondents found it difficult to answer this question. Therefore, it can be assumed that the strengths of the organizational environment of the university can be potential psychological conditions for conflict prevention.

Analysis of weaknesses - the weaknesses of the organizational environment of higher education institutions in which teachers work, as well as the "triggering" factors for the emergence of conflicts between the teaching staff include the following points: wages and working conditions, maintenance, more or less work, hard or light work. For example, "is the salary level high?" 28.3% of respondents chose the option "not at all like that", "no, not like that" - 26.7%, "not true" - 21.7%. That is, in general, 76.7% of teachers are not satisfied with the level of wages. At the same time, 61.7% called working conditions satisfactory, and 16.7% - bad. It should be noted that 43.3% of teachers believe that the technical equipment of the universities where they work is outdated. This is 1.5 times more than 28.3 percent of respondents who answered that technical support is modern.

In general, 28.3% of respondents found it difficult to answer this question. In addition to these shortcomings, we believe that special attention should be given to responses related to the relationship between teachers and management. Teachers note that the job, as if giving them the opportunity to communicate well, has a low level of satisfaction with professional relationships. This is evidenced by data showing that only 41.7% of teachers have good relations with colleagues, 45.0% - satisfactory and 13.3% of respondents - poor. As for good relations with management, this percentage is less than half; 45.0% of respondents, satisfactory relations were noted by 55.0%.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the levels and integral indicators of the development of the cognitive, emotional and behavioral components of the conflict competence of university teachers were determined. The results of the determining experiment showed that the majority of university teachers (72.7%) have an average level of development of the cognitive component of conflict competence, and only 7.9% of the study participants have a high level. The results of the experiment showed the psychological characteristics that exist in different age groups of teachers, knowledge about conflicts (development of the cognitive component of conflict competence) increases with age. When assessing the level of development of the emotional component using the methodology for assessing the psychological situation in the team, assessing the level of reactive and personal anxiety, the following results were achieved:

- a) the majority of university teachers have a low level of reactive anxiety, but an average and high level of personal anxiety;
- b) the majority of participants in the study assess the psychological situation in the team at a low and medium level.

As for personal anxiety, we can observe different levels of anxiety in groups of teachers of different sexes. Men have more personal concerns than women. The results of the study also showed that the level of personal anxiety increases with age, depending on the type of institution in which the respondents work and the subject they teach. A high level of personal anxiety was found in 45.7% of teachers of higher educational institutions, among Hungarian teachers this figure was 30.0%. The assessment of the psychological situation in the team depends on the characteristics of teachers, such as marital status, age, nationality, type of educational institution and teaching discipline.

The results of the experiment showed that unmarried teachers (38.0%), compared with 29.2% of married teachers, highly appreciate the psychological situation in the team. It is noted that the assessment of the environment in the team varies depending on age. Teachers over 30 rate it higher than younger teachers. These studies have shown that teachers of social sciences, all participants in the experiment, rate the psychological situation in the team almost twice as high as teachers of the humanities.

The results obtained showed that the majority of teachers of higher educational institutions (45.8%) have an average, 25% - a low level of emotional development. But only 29.2% of teachers have a highly developed emotional component.

When assessing the level of development of the behavioral component, the following results were obtained:

- a) the average level of conflict resistance of most teachers;
- b) the majority of study participants have an average level of aggressiveness;

c) "avoidance" is used by teachers as a method of behavior in conflict, and "cooperation" is used by the smallest number of teachers. The results of the experiment showed that the degree of use of the methods of "cooperation" and "competition" is determined by such a factor as nationality. "Cooperation" is more used by teachers of higher educational institutions.

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